

FORMATION OF KNOWLEDGE OF FUTURE TEACHERS ON INFORMATION SECURITY BASED ON A CYBERNETIC APPROACH

B.J. Matchanov

Urganch State University, senior teacher of the department of the "Computer Science",
independent researcher of Tashkent State Pedagogical University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14840720>

Abstract. *This article examines in detail how the use of a cybernetic approach to modeling the pedagogical process in the field of information security contributes to improving the effectiveness of the educational process.*

Keywords: *cybernetics, cybernetic approach, principles of cybernetics, programmed education, systematic approach, information security*

Modern computers can be used not only as a powerful tool for optimization and efficiency improvement, but also as a tool for committing illegal actions. Information security threats have become a constant threat to all organizations, regardless of the industry they operate in [1].

Teaching the subject "Information Security Fundamentals" to students of the educational programs "Computer Science and Programming Technologies" and "Information Security" in a higher educational institution is associated with difficulties due to the dynamics of the development of these programs. The classroom teaching format has a number of features associated with different levels of knowledge and experience in using information technology. The knowledge, skills and abilities obtained as a result of mastering the discipline "Information Security Fundamentals" will help the future specialist in his future professional activities in working with information constituting a state, official or educational secret. Therefore, it is important for the teacher to choose pedagogical technologies that optimize the learning process and identify interdisciplinary connections for the formation of competencies in the field of information security. In our opinion, the use of the cybernetic approach in modeling the pedagogical process in such an active area as information security can contribute to increasing the effectiveness of the learning process.

Understanding the meaning of the term "*cybernetic approach*" should begin with understanding the term "cybernetics". The term was first introduced in 1948 by the American mathematician, "the father of cybernetics" Norbert Wiener in his famous book "Cybernetics, or Control and Communication in the Animal and the Machine". Norbert Wiener, analyzing the results of applied research in various scientific fields, came to the conclusion that the same problems arise everywhere. He set himself the goal of "combining efforts in various fields of science, directing them to a common solution to similar problems" [4]. If you know how to control a system, it will definitely work successfully. The author of the theory himself defined cybernetics as "the theory of control and communication in machines and living organisms" [3].

The basic principles, or sometimes called laws, of cybernetics were developed at different times by scientists such as William Ashby and Stafford Beer. Fedosyuk Ya.V., Kashina O.A. and

Evseeva Yu.I., based on their work, a table of principles of cybernetics was compiled (Figure 1) [6,7,8].

Figure 1. Principles of Cybernetics

law of requisite variety – the diversity of a complex system requires control, which in itself has some diversity (W.R. Ashby);

principle of inference – the larger the system and the greater the difference in size between the part and the whole, the greater the likelihood that the properties of the whole will differ from the properties of the parts (W.R. Ashby);

principle of external supplementation (or "black box") – any control system needs a "black box", that is, compensation for the unaccounted influence of the external and internal environment with the help of certain reserves (A.S. Beer);

principle of feedback – the impossibility of organizing effective control on scientific principles without feedback between interconnected and interacting elements, parts or systems;

principle of decision selection – decision making based on the choice of one of several options;

principle of decomposition – the fact that the controlled object can always be considered as consisting of subsystems (parts) that are relatively independent of each other (W.E. Ashby and G. Klaus);

principles of hierarchy of control and automatic regulation – multi-level control is typical for complex systems: at higher levels there are different flows of information and their processing takes more time, therefore the speed of decision-making at lower levels is higher.

As can be seen from figure 1, the principles of cybernetics, outlined in the middle of the last century, can be applied to describe any complex system. For example, the study of the subject "Fundamentals of Information Security" by students of the educational programs "Computer

Science and Programming Technologies" and "Information Security" can also be considered using the categories and principles of cybernetics.

The cybernetic approach in pedagogy began to be applied in the 1950s. Initially, the form of programmed learning was developed by B.F. Skinner. The scientist writes in his book "Technology of Teaching" (1968): "Simply leading the student to a solution in the traditional way is a kind of programming by solving in the traditional way " [2]. When Skinner talks about programmed learning, he explains that an experienced teacher sees when a student is ready to move on to the next stage of learning. Otherwise, the student remains at this stage until he is ready to move on to the next stage[2]. The principle of programmed learning echoes the principle of cybernetic feedback, without which it is impossible to manage such a complex system as the educational process.

In Soviet pedagogy, Kolmogorov A.N., Itelson A.B., Berg A.I., Arkhangelsky S.I., Bespalko V.P., Fedorov B.I., Babansky Yu.K., Boltyansky V.G., Blauberg N.V., Sadovsky V.N., Yudin E.G. and others applied the principles of cybernetics[5].

Using a systems approach, cybernetics allows for the analysis and management of complex processes, taking into account the relationships between parts of the system, as well as external influences on it, in order to make optimal decisions to achieve the goal. The cybernetic approach helps to effectively analyze and manage the learning process to achieve the best results thanks to the mechanisms and tools for studying and modeling complex systems. The development of information technology not only helps to collect, transmit and process information, but also makes decision-making more effective when analyzing the learning process and achieving planned results.

In order to help future ICT teachers apply a cybernetic approach to managing the process of teaching the subject "Fundamentals of Information Security", it is necessary to define the goals and objectives of training, the level of initial knowledge, skills and qualifications of students, and to achieve high results in a short time. To do this, it is necessary to choose the forms and methods of organizing the educational process, use information and digital educational technologies in managing the educational process (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Cybernetic approach to teaching the basics of information security

When defining the goals and objectives of teaching the discipline "Basics of Information Security", the qualification requirements for the training of bachelors in the areas of education in the field of ICT and the requirements for personnel imposed by the labor market were taken into account.

The *purpose* of the subject "Basics of Information Security" is to teach students the principles of ensuring the information security of the state, analyzing its information infrastructure and solving the problems of ensuring the information security of computer systems, as well as to teach students to understand the complexities of modern enterprises and organizations, taking into account the basic requirements of information security. The goal is to develop sustainable skills in working in a network information environment.

The main *objectives* of the subject "Basics of Information Security" are: teaching the basics of creating information security systems, teaching the basics of creating a security policy program, teaching the basics of assessing the security of computer systems, teaching methods and means of ensuring security, as well as teaching information security of computer systems. The current state of information security issues, existing threats, types of information security, methods and means of information protection, the basics of legal regulation of relations in the information sphere, constitutional guarantees of citizens' rights to information and mechanisms for their implementation, concepts and types of protected information.

The subject "Fundamentals of Information Security" is included in the mandatory block of subjects of the curriculum of the training areas "Computer Science and Programming Technologies" and "Information Security". Taking into account the demand for qualifications in the field of education, in the labor market, as well as the developed course scheme, as a result of studying the discipline "Fundamentals of Information Security" the student will be able to:

- *have knowledge* of regulatory documents in the field of information security, threats to information security, formal and informal means of information protection, methods of identification and authentication of users, principles of creating an electronic digital signature, hashing algorithms, symmetric and asymmetric encryption methods and systems of protection against malware;

- *analyze* sources of threats and channels of information leakage, apply the most effective methods and means of information protection, develop organizational measures for information protection, monitor the *effectiveness of protective measures*.

- *to have experience* working with information security terminology, technologies for combating information security threats, protecting information from computer viruses and malware, skills in choosing and configuring information security software, interpreting results and analyzing data from system logs of security tools.

The specificity of the goals, objectives, required knowledge, skills and qualifications is such that it is difficult to fully cover the areas of information security in one semester of study with a small number of students. This problem can be solved using the following factors:

- students must have experience in using information technologies;
- teaching subjects must be closely related to the discipline "Fundamentals of Information Security" to students of the first cycle of secondary schools and higher educational institutions;
- using new pedagogical technologies in lessons and information support for the learning process;
- presentation of scientific resources in various forms (graphic, audio, video);
- activating independent activities of students;
- interaction between teachers and students.

Within the framework of the subject "Fundamentals of Information Security" it is necessary to instill interest in this subject throughout the entire period of study. From the very first lesson,

students should be told about the fundamental changes occurring in the information process, its digitization, as well as the benefits and threats associated with this. A review of the doctrines and concepts of information security in developed countries allows us to understand the importance of knowledge and skills in using information security tools not only in the practical activities of future ICT specialists, but also in the daily practice of every person.

It is also necessary to convey to students that cybersecurity competencies occupy a special place in the European Competency Framework, the Russian Digital Literacy Index, and the Concept of Information Security of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Information security and computer data protection have long been part of information technology; its basics should be studied starting from school, and a person's competence should be improved throughout life.

Using the cybernetic approach, it is possible to adapt didactic methods, topics of theoretical and practical work taking into account the initial level of knowledge of ICT students in the field of information security and the results of feedback data analysis during the learning process.

In our opinion, the development of a cybernetic approach to teaching future specialists the basics of information security in the context of a limited number of classroom hours and a large volume of educational data significantly improves the quality of education. Since the cybernetic approach studies the system, information processes occur to store and process data used for management and regulation. As a result, a pedagogical model for teaching the subject "Fundamentals of Information Security" to students majoring in "Computer Science and Programming" and "Information Security" will be built using a systems approach.

REFERENCES

1. Matchanov B.J. Cybernetic approach to teaching the basics of information security. Information bulletin of the Urgench State Pedagogical Institute, No. 2.2023, ISSN / 2992-8796, pp. 103-109.
2. Skinner B.F. Technology of training. New York: Appleton-Century-Crofts. 1968, 255 p.
3. Wiener N. Cybernetics or control and communication in animals and machines, 2nd ed. Moscow: Sovetskoye Radio, 1968. 328 p.
4. Novikov D.A. Cybernetics: Navigator. History of cybernetics, current state, development prospects. Moscow: LENAND, 2016. 160 p. ISBN 978-5-9710-2549-8.
5. Chibakov A.S. Cybernetic approach to learning: historical, evolutionary and essential aspects. In: Technical sciences / "Colloquium-journal". 2019, No. 27 (51), pp. 49-53. ISSN 2520-6990
6. Evseeva Yu.I. Software cybernetics: current state and problems. In: News of higher educational institutions. Volga region. Technical sciences. 2017, No. 3 (43), pp. 48-59. ISSN 2072-3059.
7. Kashina O.A. On the implementation of general principles of cybernetics in the innovative development of an engineering university. In: Educational technologies and society. 2018, No. 3 (vol. 21), pp. 284-289. ISSN 1436-4522.
8. Fedosyuk Ya.V. Regularities and principles of cybernetics as a theoretical and methodological basis for the formation of management teams. In: Electronic scientific and practical journal "Scientific Result". Sociology and Management. 2015, No. 3, pp. 89-92. ISSN 2408-9338.